

Philosophical Solutions to Unsolved Mathematical Framework of Variables

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1 Collatz Conjecture

$$3x + 1$$

$$x/2$$

$$C(\infty) = (3x + 1)/(x/2) - \infty$$

$$C(2\infty) = 4/2$$

$$C(\infty) = 2/2$$

$$C(\infty) = 1$$

Hence,

Proved.

2 Goldbach Conjecture

x (Even no. Greater than 2)

y and z (Prime no.)

$$G(\infty) = (y + z)/x$$

$$G(x \cdot \infty) = y + z$$

Hence,

Proved.

3 The Twin Prime Conjecture

y and z (twin primes, where $y < z$)

$$P(\infty) = y + 2 = z$$

$$P(\infty) = (y + 2)/z$$

$$P(\infty) - 2 = y + z$$

Hence,

Proved.